

A large version of the HIBLend logo, with the 'H' in purple, 'B' in red, 'L' in purple, and 'Lend' in dark purple. A red star is above the 'B'.

Deliverable 3.1

HIBLend - Quality perceptions and QA approaches to Student Blended Mobility

Project Acronym	HIBLend
Project title	Fostering high-quality blended student mobility in higher education
Starting date	01/01/2023
Duration	36 months
Call identifier	ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PCOOP-ENGO
Grant Agreement	101090715

Deliverable details	
Work Package	WP3
Deliverable Number	D3.1
Deliverable Name	HIBLend - Quality perceptions and QA approaches to Student Blended Mobility
Lead Beneficiary	Academic Cooperation Association
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Due Date	31.08.2024
Actual Submission	05.02.2025

Type of Deliverable	Document, Report
Dissemination Level	Public

Revision History			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	10/01/2025	All partners	Mini Delphi results
1.0	22/01/2025	Mark Frederiks, Dagmar Provijn	Review and chapters 1, 4 and 5
2.0	24/01/2025	Mark Frederiks, Dagmar Provijn	Review after feedback from ACA
3.0	27/01/2025	Angeliki Psychogyiou	Final draft for partners feedback
4.0	05/02/2025	Angeliki Psychogyiou	Finalisation after feedback

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
ACA	Academic Cooperation Association
BIPs	Blended Intensive Programmes
ESG	Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area
EUAs	European Universities Alliances
EUF	European University Foundation
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IRO	International Relations Officers
MU	Masaryk University
NA	National Agencies for Erasmus+
NVAO	Accreditation Organisation of the Netherlands and Flanders
QA	Quality Assurance
SBM	Student Blended Mobility
TAMK	Tampere University of Applied Sciences

1. Introduction

Higher Education Institutions have increasingly experimented with diverse formats, including those applied to student mobility, in response to the significant rise in digitalisation over the past decades. This has led to the emergence of Student Blended Mobility (SBM), which was also fostered by the digital transformation due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the EU Digital Education Action Plan and the European Universities Initiative. The Erasmus Programme Guide (2022) defines SBM as a “Combination of physical mobility and virtual elements, where students engage in both face-to face and online learning experiences in an international context as part of their study programmes”. However, HEIs often lack experience and struggle to develop high-quality SBM, applying the same quality assurance (QA) principles to SBM as for regular educational provision and mobility schemes. The HIBLend project aims to increase interest in SBM and to enhance HEIs’ capacity to develop high-quality SBM.

The HIBLend WP 2 report “Approaches to Student Blended Mobility”, which was published in the first phase of the project, provides a comprehensive exploration and categorisation of theoretical and practical approaches to SBM formats. A literature review highlighted the key features of SBM with their respective benefits and shortcomings, the problem-based or self-guided learning models, and the Erasmus+ approaches of individual bilateral blended mobility or Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs) which are based on structured institutional cooperation. SBM can also be distinguished based on their length (short-term vs long-term) and type of mobility (credit vs degree mobility).

SBM practices and approaches were further explored using a survey among HEIs, focus groups and hackathons. IRO Coordinators/Officers and Teachers/Professors were found to be key institutional actors involved in SBM, whilst Study Programme Coordinators, IT Officers, Instructional Designers/E-learning Consultants, and QA Officers were less involved. A collaborative approach, integrating academic, technological, administrative and quality assurance aspects of SBM, was found to be important for quality SBM. Offering students an increased potential for intercultural learning, attracting more students and making mobility more attractive or feasible to them were mentioned as main reasons for implementing student mobility in a blended format. Administrative staff were twice as involved in BIPs as academic staff, whilst both types of staff were equally involved in short-term SBM. The most common sequence of SBM components was where the online component preceded, facilitated and prepared the subsequent physical mobility. However, online components during physical mobility could enhance the on-site learning experience, enriching interactions and academic engagement, whilst online components after the physical mobility support reflective learning and allow for consolidation and continued engagement with the host culture. The advantage of an

online component taking place both before and after physical mobility is that it ensures in-depth preparation and post-experience reflection, thereby maximising the educational journey.

Although SBM activities are overwhelmingly funded by the Erasmus+ programme, there is mostly no funding for the online component. Only a small part of SBM (13%) tends to be part of an accredited programme. Evaluation for SBM activities is mixed: formal evaluation by the central-level or faculty-level QA office was most frequently mentioned, whilst informal assessment methods or other assessments (e.g. in the context of EUAs) also occurred. Recognition of SBM learning outcomes was a concern both for mobile and non-mobile students, with the lack of formal recognition for the online component highlighted as a special problem. Another challenge for non-mobile students (i.e. those enrolled by the host institution) is that they often do not receive any preparatory support compared to mobile students.

The study identified SBM challenges related to student engagement, technical/digital, financial/administrative, communication/coordination, pedagogical, cultural/interpersonal, and logistical challenges. Success factors for SBM are related to advanced and early planning, motivated staff and students, strong partnership communication and staff collaboration, sufficient guidance, funding and shared practices, and curriculum-embedded programmes with clear learning outcomes with an intercultural focus, engaging content and interactive pedagogy. The report ended with an overview of different types and paths of SBM, which informed the next steps in the project. Finally, the report was discussed and validated by the HIBLend Advisory Board, composed of seven distinguished experts in higher education, quality assurance, student mobility, and internationalisation, who provide strategic guidance to enhance the project's impact and visibility in the European Higher Education Area.

The next phase of the HIBLend project, as presented in the current WP 3 report, explores the quality considerations of SBM and the institutional approaches to QA from a multi-stakeholder perspective, involving the key internal and external actors. To this end a mini-Delphi study has been conducted with expert/stakeholder sessions to harvest data on quality considerations regarding SBM. The methodology for this mini-Delphi study is explained in Chapter 2. In Chapter 3, the results of the mini-Delphi sessions are presented from the perspective of relevant organisational, student, pedagogical and external actors. The main quality themes for SBM are derived from these findings in Chapter 4. The report ends with conclusions and recommendations that will aid the development of a comprehensive framework for supporting institutions in delivering high-quality SBM activities.

The purpose of the current WP 3 report “Quality perceptions and QA approaches to student blended mobility” is thus to summarise the findings on quality considerations and QA approaches to SBM from a university (strategic and organisational), teacher (pedagogical and technological),

student (learning experience) and external actor perspective. This report will inform the design, testing, and dissemination of a comprehensive framework offering guidance on quality considerations for existing models and approaches to SBM. It is expected that the outcomes of WP 3 will be instrumental in shaping future SBM initiatives and ensuring their success and sustainability.

2. Methodology

A mini-Delphi study was set up to gain insights from a stakeholder’s perspective regarding the relevant quality issues for SBM. To reduce complexity, it was decided not to mix groups but organise separate sessions for each stakeholder group. Each project partner was responsible for organising a session with a specific stakeholder group. These sessions were held online with a limited number of participants to ensure that each participant was heard, and a dialogue could ensue. After each session the main results were reported so that it could inform the next session with stakeholders. This reporting constituted the iterative part of the mini-Delphi study.

First, a concept note was developed outlining the structure and approach for the mini-Delphi sessions. The concept note highlighted for the project partners the different procedural steps, the set-up and follow-up for the mini-Delphi sessions, an interview guide and the guiding questions for each session with stakeholders. This way, a common approach for organising the online sessions could be ensured.

The five stakeholders’ groups that were interviewed were designated as the most relevant ones following the WP2: Approaches to Student Blended Mobility report: administrative staff/management, academic staff, students, NAs and national funders for SBM, and QA agencies. The mini-Delphi study covered thus the institutional (strategic and organisational), teacher (pedagogical and technological), student (learning experience), and external actor (national funders and Erasmus+/QA agencies) perspectives. Each project partner organised online sessions according to its acquaintance with the stakeholder groups, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Stakeholder group sessions and responsible lead partner

LEAD PARTNER	STAKEHOLDER GROUP
EU	administrative staff/management
TAMK	academic staff involved in SBM
MU	students involved in SBM
NVAO	QA agencies
ACA	Erasmus+ officers Officers of regional/national funding schemes

As a result, 5 online sessions were held, although in some cases sessions were organised in two parts so that all questions were dealt with, and all selected participants could be heard. It was the responsibility of each lead partner to select and approach up to 6 participants from their stakeholder groups, which was perceived as an appropriate number in view of the number of questions and the available session time. The selected participants had to reflect the diversity of the stakeholder group for the mini-Delphi session. A table listing all sessions and their details is presented in Annex 1. The online sessions were organised in the period September-beginning of November 2024. This timing allowed for a learning process based on several iterations of mini-Delphi sessions with sufficient intervals during which questions could be adapted and fine-tuned. The planning also enabled a discussion of the results at the HIBLend Transnational Project Meeting by mid November 2024 in Brno, Czechia.

The participants received, from the lead partner, an information note in advance of the online session. This information note, as agreed by the project partners, introduced the HIBLend project, the purpose and outline of the mini-Delphi sessions, and explained how participants could prepare for the session. Participants received the WP 2 report as background information; they were told that the report would not be an explicit point of discussion during the session but they could share their feedback on the report by sending an e-mail to the lead partner. Participants could also send information on how they were involved with SBM, or with QA of SBM, to the lead partner prior to the session. Finally, the information note contained the list of questions for the session, but it was highlighted that the intention was not to fully prepare answers to these questions in advance.

As agreed in the concept note, the online sessions were conducted through Microsoft Teams as a digital platform. The length of each session was limited to a maximum of 2 hours. The sessions were recorded and transcribed after prior approval of the participants; a consent form was developed and signed by each participant. The lead partner drafted a short summary of the session with the most important points of the discussions and the key takeaways. A reporting format was developed for this purpose. The short summaries, recordings and transcripts were placed in a special directory on the Teams HIBLend environment so that all project partners could be informed and, if relevant, the main findings could be used for the next session. The sessions were conducted in line with the interview guide and followed the guiding questions, which were both included in the concept note. The guiding questions were inspired by the results of the WP 2 report, the Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG), and the CeQulnt approach of the centrality of intercultural and international learning outcomes and their relationship with the internationalisation strategy. Separate guiding questions were developed for each stakeholder group and further adapted by each lead partner

to make it suitable and understandable for the participants in the session. The list of questions for each session with stakeholders is presented in Annex 2.

After all sessions were conducted, the reporting formats containing the summaries of the main results and the lessons learnt or issues to be aware of, were analysed. A number of quality themes emerged from the analyses which had common ground in several stakeholders' perspectives and were related to core parts of the ESG. These themes were discussed, together with the main results of the mini-Delphi sessions as presented by each lead partner, at the HIBLend project meeting in Brno. The main results are presented in Chapter 3, whilst the quality themes are discussed in Chapter 4.

3. Mini-Delphi sessions

3.1 Administration Perspectives

The EUF organised two online mini-Delphi sessions with central and faculty-level administrative and management staff involved in SBM. Six participants attended, representing institutions in Latvia, Belgium/Flanders, Poland, Finland, and Czechia. The discussion addressed the following topics: I. Institutional goals and objectives, II. Resources, III. Organisation, and IV. Quality assurance. This chapter summarises our findings in the respective topics: a) Challenges in administration, funding, and resources, b) Inter-institutional cooperation and strategic alignment, c) Role of QA systems in institutions, and d) Conclusions.

Challenges in administration, funding, and resources

Our research activities highlighted several organisational challenges that affect managing administration, funding, and resources for SBM. A primary issue is the complexity of funding mechanisms, particularly within Erasmus+. While the programme funds opportunities for SBMs, procedural limitations, such as caps on applications and the administrative burdens of registration, complicate planning, as summarised by one participant: *“This is an administrative burden and overcomplicated process because they need to register it in the next call; it prevents long-term organised planning and weakens engagement to organise them, especially the first edition.”* Some institutions have mitigated uncertainties by establishing internal backup funds, yet these are not universally available, and resources allocated for staff workloads and programme development remain insufficient. Moreover, geographic limitations further exacerbate financial strain, especially for students in less accessible locations, who typically face higher travel costs. In addition, resource gaps extend to technical and digital skills, which are critical for SBMs’ virtual component but are often underdeveloped among staff and faculty members. Lastly, structural barriers within institutions, such as inconsistent recognition of SBMs in curricula and unequal resource distribution among faculties, hinder broader adoption and integration.

Inter-institutional cooperation and strategic alignment

While some universities have successfully incorporated SBMs into their broader internationalisation strategies, others lack a clear focus, relying instead on isolated or irregular initiatives. Institutions involved in EUAs and other networks benefit from stronger alignment with sustainability and inclusion objectives. Effective cooperation also depends on establishing clear communication channels and shared frameworks; yet issues, such as harmonising academic schedules and administrative procedures between institutions, remain obstacles. What is more,

peer learning opportunities and centralised information systems are instrumental in fostering collaboration, but frequent staff turnover may undermine the continuity or success of partnerships. Furthermore, experience with previously explored initiatives, such as Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL) and summer/winter schools, offers scalable intercultural learning and collaboration opportunities. Interestingly, one participant stated that “COILs (were) a natural introduction into the SBM spectrum” for their staff and that it was crucial when joining a University Alliance.

Role of QA systems in institutions

QA systems for SBMs are still being developed across many institutions. Existing frameworks, often adapted from traditional, long-term physical mobility programmes, struggle to address the unique characteristics of SBMs, particularly the learning outcomes and evaluation of the virtual component. Student feedback collection is mainly informal, with few structured tools to monitor programme outcomes effectively. Some institutions, however, have begun using standardised questionnaires explicitly designed for SBMs, allowing for aggregated insights and targeted recommendations.

Despite these advancements, several barriers persist. Staff can find it challenging to manage international and online groups, combined with insufficient technical skills, which limits the effectiveness of QA measures. Secondly, workloads associated with SBM activities are often undervalued and lack more formal or structural recognition. “*It shouldn’t be an individual effort, but structurally recognised by a study programme,*” as another participant proposed. Compounding these challenges, national accreditation systems rarely account for SBMs, leaving gaps in formal QA processes.

Participants emphasised the importance of integrating QA into institutional practices, actively and regularly collecting feedback from staff and students, evaluating it, and engaging all relevant stakeholders, even external QA agents. Advocacy at the European level to establish standards for blended formats and accreditation was also recommended.

Concluding remarks

SBMs present a powerful opportunity to expand access to internationalisation, foster inclusivity, and promote innovation in higher education. However, their potential is contingent on addressing significant systemic barriers. Institutions require structured and consistent funding mechanisms that go beyond project-based approaches, allowing for long-term planning and integration of SBMs into curricula and study programmes. Guidelines from National and European actors should focus on reducing administrative burdens associated with Erasmus+

funding, streamlining application processes, and ensuring equitable resource allocation across faculties and institutions.

Additionally, clear frameworks for inter-institutional cooperation are needed. These should include standardised agreements on academic calendars, credit recognition, and harmonised processes for short-term and blended formats. Building robust partnerships within EUAs and networks can help scale SBMs, but institutions need support in the form of toolkits and best practices for managing these collaborations. Sharing successful case studies, such as integrating SBMs into EUAs, can provide actionable models for others to follow.

Quality assurance also demands a more structured approach. Universities should develop institutional policies that embed QA processes into the planning and execution of SBMs. Standardised feedback tools and staff training on managing blended learning environments are essential. National QA agencies must adapt their standards to include blended mobility formats, ensuring that the virtual components are adequately assessed and accredited.

Finally, universities need to prioritise capacity building for administrative and academic staff. This includes dedicated training on developing digital skills, innovative online pedagogy, and intercultural group management. Recognising the added workload associated with SBMs through workload redistribution, incentives, or formal acknowledgement can motivate faculty and staff to invest in these programmes. Policymakers should emphasise the strategic importance of SBMs in achieving broader internationalisation and inclusion goals in higher education, providing institutions with the necessary tools and frameworks to fully realise their potential.

3.2 Student Perspectives

MU held one mini-Delphi session with students from MU and students from other universities who took part in the blended courses organized by MU. The students from the partner universities were from Potsdam, Lisbon and Bologna. Overall, 15 students participated in the session. The main topics of discussion were why the blended courses were attractive to them, their feedback on the preparatory stage, online and offline teaching, intercultural and international aspects of the course, and their satisfaction with and evaluation of the courses. A special focus was put on the lessons learned based on the students' recommendations.

Insights into student preferences

Students report that they selected blended courses for a couple of reasons. Many of them put the attractiveness of the topic first and the possibility of learning it in an intensive way. They also mentioned the appeal of trying something shorter than the classical Erasmus+ mobility. Students valued physical mobility opportunities that allowed them to explore new cultures, gain practical

knowledge, and experience diverse educational settings. Students had a chance to participate in various in-person activities (site and cultural visits, trips or activities enhancing intercultural exchanges).

The programme's shorter, intensive format appealed to those looking for an alternative to traditional Erasmus programs. As their physical mobility is very short and the blended courses are organised during the semester, they miss the support, cultural orientation and contact with the other host university students, unlike the students on semester mobility. On the other hand, students had opportunities to interact with students from different parts of Europe or the World.

Engagement challenges in blended mobility

Online components were perceived as less engaging compared to the physical parts of the program. Students often cited boredom, lack of interaction, and technical issues as barriers to meaningful participation in virtual sessions. The majority of the blended courses are organized under the Erasmus+ framework and follow the Erasmus procedures and requirements. However, the Erasmus rules for these courses are very vague, and the universities manage them in different ways. Some universities provide comprehensive pre-programme information, including details on accommodation and logistics, while others struggle to address student inquiries effectively, creating frustration. It would be beneficial to have guidelines for the university staff to help them with best practices in organising these kinds of courses. Students also reported that they would appreciate having very clear rules and unified administrative support to help support them during admission, studying and evaluation.

Quality of online components versus physical components

While online components often served as preparatory stages, their effectiveness was hampered by limited interactivity. In contrast, physical sessions included dynamic activities such as site visits, trips, and hands-on projects, which were widely praised for their depth and engagement. Technical issues, such as unreliable access to online tools, further complicate student participation in online components. Very often, the BIP organizers/pedagogical facilitators focus on a very good physical programme and do not consider the online part as that important. Best practices from other colleagues could inspire them on how to organize the online component.

Some students reported being disappointed with the quality of the course as there was a last-moment replacement of the teacher who was not very experienced. It seems that in some cases, the BIP courses are not taken very seriously by the hosting university, although the expectations of the students are always very high.

The students also reported that the organizers asked for feedback, but usually only for the physical part of the programme. They had the feeling that no one enjoyed the online part, students or teachers. It is very recommended to have a short guideline or short course for teachers to learn how to work with the online part of the course and how to attract the attention of the students.

Students had some suggestions to improve the online part, such as preparing mingle/get-to-know sessions, shorter meetings, or voluntary participation.

Motivation and inclusion of domestic students

Domestic students were not included in all the BIP courses. This is very often justified by the rules of Erasmus's support. The students on mobilities receive funds for their physical mobilities, while domestic students do not get any support. Very often, this is the reason why they are not motivated to participate in the BIP courses, as the main attraction for the students is the physical component. Domestic students could be motivated by opportunities to engage with international peers, learn practical skills, and participate in culturally enriching activities. However, some domestic participants struggled with inclusivity in online sessions, where engagement often depended on proactive participation. The main recommendation of the students was to make the online component more attractive and to offer them a similar short exchange for another semester. This could require better strategic planning among the cooperating universities and their management.

3.3 Pedagogical Perspectives

TAMK organized two mini-Delphi sessions focusing on collecting the views of teachers and staff members (e.g. international coordinators) involved in blended mobility with a special focus on pedagogy. The first mini-Delphi session took place on the 13th of September, 2024 as an online meeting, and the experts taking part in the session were six teachers from TAMK who had previously been involved in blended mobility initiatives, many of them quite heavily. The second mini-Delphi session took place on the 9th of October, 2024 as an online meeting, and the experts were three international coordinators from Metropolia University of Applied Sciences.

Before the first meeting, the experts taking part in it were sent a questionnaire to fill in to chart their opinions to form a backbone for the discussion. The questionnaire included the following questions, arising from the HIBlend mid-report:

1. What kind of pedagogical methods are or could be useful and increase or ensure the quality of learning in blended mobility?

2. What kind of digital environments, applications or are or could be useful and increase or ensure the quality of learning in blended mobility?
3. What kind of digital environments and online learning methods and tools have you already successfully utilised in blended mobility?
4. How have you planned blended mobilities and what should be taken into account in planning them? What kind of structure has functioned well (e.g. the rhythm of online and physical periods)?
5. How have you tried to ensure the quality of learning in blended mobility? How are the learning objectives defined in the curriculum assessed or how could they be assessed in blended mobility?
6. Is there support and resources available in your organisation for developing or running blended mobilities? If not, what kind of support would you like to receive?
7. How does being involved in planning and running blended mobilities affect your development as a teacher or staff member? How could the new ideas and practices that are potentially born as part of this process be distributed in your organisation?

The results of this questionnaire were used to direct the first mini-Delphi session, and, in turn, the results arising from the first session were used as a basis for the second mini-Delphi session. Hence, the iterative nature of the Delphi methodology came into fruition, albeit in a slightly modified form.

The analysis

Numerous important insights were raised in the two mini-Delphi sessions. In this analysis, we have aimed at selecting the most important ones.

At the heart of pedagogical excellence lies the strategic integration of diverse teaching methods. The experts emphasized how coaching approaches, when combined with multidisciplinary learning environments, create rich educational experiences. These experiences are further enhanced when students engage with real-world challenges, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. The involvement of visiting experts through established networks adds valuable perspectives, exposing students to diverse viewpoints and industry expertise.

Team dynamics play a fundamental role in the success of blended mobility initiatives. The experts highlighted the importance of thoughtful team formation well in advance of the physical mobility period. By implementing carefully planned grouping strategies in online meetings preceding the physical mobility and incorporating team-building activities, institutions can foster an environment where meaningful collaboration flourishes and is seamlessly continued when the

intensive week commences. The importance of team building continues during physical mobility, with social events being recognized as vital components that strengthen team cohesion and cultural understanding.

The digital landscape presents both opportunities and challenges. While platforms like Zoom and Google Workspace provide robust tools for collaboration, institutions must navigate organizational restrictions and ensure accessibility for all participants. The experts stressed the importance of systematic tracking and documentation of online participation, ensuring that the digital component of blended mobility maintains high educational standards and is an integral part of the whole blended mobility.

Success in blended mobility initiatives relies heavily on meticulous planning and execution. Visual aids, such as storyboards, have proven invaluable in communicating complex information effectively. The experts emphasized the necessity of integrating financial and pedagogical planning from the outset, ensuring that educational goals align with available resources. Communication strategies must be tailored to different stakeholder groups, with particular attention paid to providing comprehensive welcome packages for incoming participants.

Quality assurance in learning outcomes requires careful consideration of assessment methods. The implementation of clear pass/fail systems, coupled with detailed grading based on comprehensive feedback, ensures transparency in evaluation. The experts noted the importance of establishing common ground in assessment scales across participating institutions, as these may vary significantly between educational systems.

The role of organizational support cannot be understated. The experts identified the need for robust support systems to navigate the complexities of international mobility bureaucracy. This includes strengthening collaboration between international units and degree programme units both within and between institutions. Financial support for educators managing blended mobility initiatives was highlighted as crucial for sustainable implementation.

Professional development emerged as a significant benefit of blended mobility programmes. The experts reported enhanced networking opportunities, increased motivation, and greater confidence in international teaching contexts. They also emphasized the importance of involving new personnel in these initiatives, ensuring knowledge transfer and sustainability of programmes.

Strategic alignment between institutional goals and blended mobility initiatives is essential for long-term success. The experts advocated for greater visibility of blended mobility in institutional

strategies and unit objectives. This alignment ensures sustained commitment to quality education and international collaboration.

Knowledge sharing and defining roles clearly emerged as critical factors in a successful implementation. Regular meetings and diverse coaching approaches, supported by appropriate technology, facilitate continuous development and improvement. The experts stressed that clearly defined roles help avoid confusion and enhance programme efficiency.

These insights from Finnish HEIs provide valuable guidance for developing and maintaining high-quality blended mobility programmes. The comprehensive approach, encompassing pedagogical, technical, organizational, and strategic considerations, offers a framework for institutions seeking to enhance their international education offerings through blended mobility.

Recommendations for Future Development

Based on the analysis of these mini-Delphi sessions, the following factors should be considered from a pedagogical perspective when planning and implementing SBM:

Pedagogical and digital aspects should be carefully integrated to ensure a coherent and effective learning experience. The selection of methods should be guided by their effectiveness in fostering student engagement and achieving learning objectives. The composition of teams should be strategically planned to enhance collaboration and leverage diverse expertise. The choice and use of digital tools should be aligned with pedagogical goals and adapted to the needs of both students and educators.

Thorough planning and execution are essential for the success of blended mobility initiatives. Comprehensive planning should address all stages of the mobility experience, from preparation to follow-up. Clear and structured communication between all stakeholders is crucial to maintaining alignment and ensuring smooth implementation. Quality assurance mechanisms should be embedded in the learning process to monitor progress and enhance outcomes. Assessment strategies should be designed to effectively measure student learning and development. Regular feedback should be encouraged to support continuous improvement and adaptation.

Institutional support plays a key role in the successful implementation of SBM. Adequate support structures should be in place to assist educators and students throughout the process. The visibility of blended mobility initiatives should be enhanced to increase awareness and engagement among relevant stakeholders. Professional development opportunities should be promoted to enhance educators' skills and maximise the impact of blended mobility on their professional growth. The dissemination of knowledge and best practices should be prioritised to

extend the benefits beyond the immediate participants. Lastly, ensuring synergy between institutional strategy and the execution of blended mobility initiatives is essential for sustainability and long-term impact.

3.4 External Actor Perspectives

3.4.1 Quality Assurance Agencies

NVAO organized two online mini-Delphi sessions and received one written response based on the same set of questions that was used in the mini-Delphi sessions. Six quality assurance agencies were involved in total: A3ES (Portugal) (written response), ARACIS (Romania), AQU Catalunya (Spain), FINEEC (Finland), HAKA (Estonia) (separate session) and QQI (Ireland). The set of questions was designed to provide a systematic understanding of quality assurance issues related to SBM and explore both current practices and potential future directions for internal and external quality assurance.

Experience of quality assurance agencies with SBM

Most agencies report limited or no direct experience with SBM specifically. They often focus on blended learning as a broader concept, recognizing its relevance but not treating SBM as a distinct area in assessments or quality assurance frameworks. Some agencies emphasize the overlap between blended learning and blended mobility, suggesting the latter is an extension of existing practices. HAKA also highlights the 'Digital Education Quality Label' they offer which indirectly addresses blended approaches.

Agencies note that the pandemic accelerated the adoption of blended practices, including mobility alternatives. Erasmus mobility and standards for mixed mobility are specifically cited, and it is mentioned how the public health crisis encouraged reliance on e-learning and online tools.

There are national differences in experiences and approaches; some focus on Erasmus KA1 BIPs as established practices, others see SBM as significant to HEIs' internationalisation strategies and recognize a future need to incorporate this into their quality assurance models.

The importance of clarifying the concept of SBM and its quality assurance implications is stressed. Guidelines and shared frameworks are seen as essential tools for supporting HEIs in implementing high-quality blended mobility programmes. There is a shared acknowledgment across agencies that current quality assurance procedures often focus on physical mobility. While digital and blended approaches are recognized, guidelines for blended mobility need further development to support its growth.

In conclusion, while there is growing recognition of the importance of SBM, most agencies remain in early stages of incorporating it into their assessments. Lessons from blended learning, guidelines for e-learning, and existing Erasmus programmes like KA1 BIPs offer a foundation for future quality assurance practices. There is a consensus on the need for further conceptual clarity, guidelines, and frameworks to help institutions fully embrace SBM.

Quality issues that should be addressed

Quality assurance for SBM requires addressing several key challenges to ensure both internal and external processes align effectively. Agencies emphasize the following.

Ensuring that physical and virtual components of SBM are integrated seamlessly is crucial for maximizing the student experience and learning outcomes. This requires robust curriculum design and strategic planning that account for hybrid education's unique nature.

A strong technological infrastructure is essential to ensure equal access for all students, regardless of socioeconomic or geographical background. Agencies highlight the need for technical support, as well as digital and pedagogical skills training for both students and faculty, to enable effective participation in virtual components.

SBM activities must align with institutional strategies for internationalisation, including partnerships, cooperation frameworks, and programme guidelines. Clear integration into institutional actions ensures SBM's long-term sustainability and impact.

Developing and assessing specific learning outcomes, including intercultural skills and digital competences, is a challenge that needs more attention. Clear frameworks for assessing these competencies are critical for meaningful quality assurance processes.

Agencies emphasize the importance of regular monitoring and feedback loops (PDCA cycle). Effective SBM quality assurance must incorporate student feedback systems to evaluate satisfaction and identify gaps, and teacher feedback systems for continuous improvement and alignment of goals. The need for administrative structures and clear procedures to guide, monitor, and evaluate student experiences is highlighted.

Agencies recognize that guidelines for SBM are in development. Existing codes for transnational and online learning provide a foundation, but these will require significant updates and adaptations as the SBM field evolves.

In conclusion, addressing the quality issues in SBM requires an integrated approach combining technological readiness, clear predetermined learning objectives, alignment with internationalisation strategies, and robust monitoring systems. By focusing on digital

competence, administrative clarity, and continuous feedback, agencies and institutions can ensure that SBM meets high standards of quality and inclusion.

Relevance of the ESG for SBM

The Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area ([ESG 2015](#)) provide a comprehensive framework for ensuring the quality of SBM. Specific elements from ESG Part 1 are particularly relevant:

1.2 Design and Approval of Programmes: Critical for ensuring seamless integration between the physical and virtual components of the mobility programme. This involves curriculum design and development that accounts for the unique challenges and opportunities of blended mobility.

1.3 Student-centred Learning, Teaching, and Assessment: Focuses on fostering effective, engaging, and innovative learning methods while enhancing the overall student experience. This includes assessing students' intercultural and digital skills, which are key learning outcomes of SBM.

1.5 Teaching Staff: Emphasizes the need for teaching staff to acquire and apply IT skills and digital pedagogical competencies. This ensures that faculty are well-equipped to support the blended aspects of mobility.

1.6 Learning Resources and Student Support: Stresses the importance of providing robust technological infrastructure, administrative support, and training for both students and staff. Adequate IT resources and technological solutions are foundational for the successful implementation of SBM.

1.7 Information Management: Highlights the need to establish systematic methods for tracking, collecting, and analyzing data on mobility, such as participation rates, learning outcomes, and overall quality. This supports continuous improvement in SBM delivery.

The importance of addressing policy-level issues is stressed by some. Policies should support digital and physical mobility, academic staff development, and the integration of mobility into broader institutional strategies for teaching and learning. Institutional and external quality assurance frameworks need to account for the specific demands of digital and hybrid delivery in mobility programmes.

In conclusion, the ESG provide a robust foundation for addressing the quality assurance challenges of SBM. Key areas of focus include curriculum design, faculty training, IT support, learning resource availability, and systematic monitoring and reporting. By aligning both internal

and external QA processes with these ESG standards, institutions can effectively support and sustain high-quality blended mobility programmes.

Integrated approach to external quality assurance of SBM

To effectively organize external quality assurance for SBM, it is essential to consider its alignment with existing quality assurance frameworks, while addressing its unique aspects. SBM should be integrated into existing institutional and programme-level quality assurance mechanisms rather than creating standalone quality assurance frameworks. This ensures alignment with current accreditation processes, reduces duplication, and emphasizes SBM as a core institutional practice. Existing cycles of institutional audits should provide flexibility to include SBM elements. At programme-level, the focus could be on ensuring the cohesion between virtual and physical learning components in curriculum design.

Emphasizing voluntary participation, enhancement-led approaches could ensure flexibility for HEIs aiming to strengthen their SBM strategies. These approaches encourage continuous improvement without penalizing institutions not yet fully aligned.

Building institutional support systems can significantly enhance quality assurance outcomes. Fostering such environments ensures consistent improvement across courses and programmes. For example, HAKA's quality labels for e-courses and associated seminars provide detailed feedback, boosting the development of courses even if they do not initially meet the criteria.

Some agencies emphasize the importance of ongoing dialogue. Quality assurance agencies can prompt HEIs to consider and develop internal quality assurance practices for SBM, particularly for small-scale initiatives likely to grow over time.

Another proposal is a workshop model as a way to establish productive dialogue with HEIs, ensuring internal quality assurance systems align with the goals of external quality assurance.

Whilst EUAs may stimulate SBM, the QA agencies are not at the forefront of this development.

Recognition of SBM activities requires clarity in learning outcomes and integration into programmes and qualifications. Institutions must adopt objective criteria for student mobility, ensuring recognition and validation of learning experiences through transparent processes. For recognition to work effectively, SBM activities must be firmly integrated into programme design and qualifications. Institutions should develop partnerships that establish transparent and comparable procedures for credit transfer and competency validation. Full recognition of SBM activities will require aligning policies on blended, virtual, and physical exchanges, leveraging existing tools like learning agreements and European-level frameworks.

In sum, for systems that rely heavily on institutional reviews/accreditations, focusing on the course level – where SBM activities predominantly occur – can pose significant challenges. However, incorporating SBM into internal quality assurance systems and aligning it with institutional internationalization policies offers a more practical approach. Developmental activities, often guided by QA agencies, can complement this integration, fostering systemic readiness for SBM without overcomplicating quality assurance processes. External quality assurance should in fact act as an enhancement-led mechanism, guiding HEIs to develop their internal systems robustly and autonomously, ensuring long-term effectiveness. The Estonian quality label for e-courses which is accompanied with enhancement activities could be a worthwhile combination of external and internal quality assurance for SBM.

3.4.2 Funding organisations

The Mini-Delphi sessions run by ACA included two critical stakeholder groups: **Erasmus+ Officers** and **National/Regional Programme Coordinators** from mobility schemes like Nordplus, CEEPUS (Central European Exchange Program for University Studies), and SEMP (Swiss-European Mobility Programme). These stakeholders play key roles in shaping funding policies and implementing SBM activities, offering distinct but complementary perspectives. By engaging with these external actors, the Mini-Delphi sessions aimed to:

- Identify funding requirements and structural design considerations for SBM activities.
- Understand the expected outcomes of SBM, such as learning achievements, intercultural competence, and inclusivity.
- Explore QA approaches, challenges, and opportunities in aligning SBM with institutional, national, and European priorities.

Their insights are essential for understanding the challenges and opportunities in quality assurance for SBM at both European and regional levels.

Structural Design of SBM

The Erasmus+ programme, the European Union's flagship initiative for education and mobility, offers comprehensive support for a range of mobility formats, including short-term blended activities like BIPs. The programme offers a standardised framework for SBM activities, with clear requirements for physical mobility (minimum 5 days, 3 ECTS workload for BIPs). The recommended workload for BIPs is 3 ECTS credits, ensuring alignment with European academic standards (ECHE). The virtual components though lack detailed guidelines, resulting in varied implementation and quality across institutions (National agencies, such as OeAD (Austria), AMEUP (Croatia) and EDUFI (Finland) noted that while institutions include a virtual component, the quality and depth of these components often depend on individual institutional practices

rather than strict guidelines. For example, while in the first round of applications for BIPs HEIs were to indicate how many working hours the virtual component was, the requirement was removed from subsequent calls). There is a strong alignment with inclusion, sustainability, and digital competence that is promoted within the programme supporting SBM but not enforced, leading to inconsistent adoption.

Regional and national mobility schemes, such as Nordplus, CEEPUS, and SEMP, cater to specific geographic or institutional contexts. While not all regional programmes explicitly support SBM, they provide valuable insights into alternative approaches to mobility and quality assurance. The schemes for the time being are primarily experimenting with blended elements in their mobility opportunities, exploring ways of integrating them into their regular offerings.

- **Nordplus:** Offers flexible short-term mobility options (e.g., express mobility) where virtual components are integrated as best practices rather than requirements.
- **CEEPUS:** Decentralised funding model allows country-specific criteria; some countries (e.g., Hungary) pilot innovative blended formats for teaching mobility, but these are not widespread.
- **SEMP:** Aligns closely with Erasmus+ standards, requiring a minimum of 3 ECTS credits for BIPs (with exceptions for teacher education) but focuses on pilot implementation of BIPs, with ongoing consultations to establish clearer structural guidelines.

Overall, virtual components tend to be more regulated in Erasmus+ but remain loosely implemented, whereas regional schemes rely on institutional initiative to integrate them within mobility activities, rather than having any requirements at programme level.

Alignment with Institutional and National Priorities

The degree to which SBM aligns with institutional and national priorities—such as inclusion, sustainability, and digital competence—varies across programmes. Erasmus+ promotes alignment with the horizontal priorities, notably inclusion, digital competence, and sustainability. However, specific measures to enforce this alignment are limited. Reporting templates allow institutions to indicate priority alignment for activities like BIPs, but there is no obligation to demonstrate their implementation. Regional/national programmes provide a more tailored approach to aligning SBM with local priorities, such as emphasising regional cooperation, linguistic and cultural goals, and emerging national priorities like STEM education.

Learning and Intercultural Competence

SBM activities, particularly through Erasmus+ BIPs, effectively enhance intercultural competence and collaboration among students. However, their short duration reportedly limits the

measurable academic impact. This does not necessarily mean that the NAs or universities can't measure it. It perhaps signifies a lack of instruments to monitor such impact. In regional programmes, like Nordplus and CEEPUS, in terms of blended mobility, the schemes do not seem to have any purposeful strategy in place yet. The focus seems to be on experimentation, without any regulatory or strategic frameworks attached.

Regional schemes adopt diverse approaches to enhancing accessibility. Nordplus and CEEPUS provide targeted funding mechanisms for underrepresented groups, including students with disabilities. For example, Nordplus covers 100% of real costs, while CEEPUS incorporates gender balance as an evaluation criterion and provides additional financial support for vulnerable groups. However, these measures are often underutilised due to low levels of promotion and awareness among institutions and students. Similarly, SEMP offers funding for sustainable travel and disability support but faces challenges in raising awareness and encouraging uptake. These findings highlight the need for proactive strategies to ensure that SBM reaches a broader and more diverse student population.

Flexibility and Inclusivity

One of the key strengths of SBM lies in its ability to offer flexible learning opportunities for students who face barriers to traditional long-term mobility. Erasmus+ has positioned blended mobility as an accessible option for students with professional or personal constraints, such as those balancing work commitments or caregiving responsibilities. Challenges persist though in ensuring satisfaction with virtual components, as demonstrated by lower student satisfaction compared to physical mobility (Finnish data indicate that only 60% of students were satisfied with the virtual aspects of BIPs, compared to 78% satisfaction for their physical counterparts).

While programmes like Erasmus+, Nordplus, and SEMP provide funding for students with special needs, low institutional awareness and promotion limit the effectiveness of these inclusivity measures. Proactive strategies, including targeted promotion and capacity-building, are essential to make SBM more accessible and equitable for all students. Additionally, integrating inclusivity metrics into programme design and evaluation frameworks would encourage institutions to prioritise accessibility and equity in their SBM activities.

Metrics, Indicators, and Gaps in Evaluating SBM Quality

Existing QA practices in Erasmus+ focus heavily on quantitative metrics like participation rates and funding utilisation, with limited attention to qualitative outcomes such as learning quality or the integration of virtual components – existence of integrated learning outcomes on both components of a blended mobility. Regional and national schemes exhibit similar patterns.

In terms of external quality assurance, the Erasmus+ programme encourages alignment with the European Standards and Guidelines, but their implementation of application to SBM needs to be further articulated. For instance, Austrian institutions are required to submit certificates of stay or transcripts of records, but these documents often do not detail the quality of the virtual component. Institutions are expected to follow the same quality standards as other mobility activities, but the unique challenges of integrating virtual and physical components are not yet fully addressed in evaluation methods. While existing measures aim to ensure compliance with the European Charter for Higher Education (ECHE), a dedicated QA framework specifically for blended mobility should be considered? Further to this, while Erasmus+ encourages alignment with general QA frameworks, such as the European Standards and Guidelines (ESG), the absence of dedicated QA processes for blended formats often results in inconsistent implementation. Similarly, regional schemes, while offering flexibility, lack standardised metrics for assessing the quality of SBM, particularly its virtual components.

Both Erasmus+ and regional schemes have traditionally emphasised physical mobility, and while the virtual component has gained importance, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, the development of robust QA practices for virtual learning is still in its infancy. In terms of internal quality assurance, institutions may lack the expertise or resources to effectively evaluate virtual learning experiences, leading to gaps. Further to this, the administrative burden of reporting discourages institutions from conducting comprehensive quality assessments, particularly for blended formats.

Challenges Identified by Stakeholders

One of the most significant challenges in SBM is the disparity in regulations and institutional capacities across countries and regions. Within the Erasmus+ programme, stakeholders pointed to the difficulty of applying standardised guidelines across diverse institutional contexts. For example, differences in the interpretation of virtual component requirements lead to inconsistent implementation. Austrian institutions often see the virtual component as a supplementary activity, while Finnish institutions place greater emphasis on its integration into the broader learning experience.

Regional and national schemes face similar obstacles but due to their decentralised nature, perhaps a central regulatory framework is not needed in this case. It is interesting to note though that since such schemes don't yet implement SBM in a cohesive way, there is perhaps a lack of awareness of the strategic benefits of blended mobility.

Limited digital infrastructure also emerged as a recurring challenge, particularly in less resourced institutions and regions. The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted these differences, as many

institutions struggled to transition to virtual learning environments. While some stakeholders view blended mobility as an opportunity to modernise digital capabilities, others caution that such initiatives may exacerbate existing inequalities.

Administrative burdens are also another key obstacle. Institutions frequently report to the NAs that the detailed reporting requirements associated with Erasmus+ discourage them from adopting innovative approaches to SBM.

Opportunities for Innovation and Good Practices

SBM serves as a platform for experimenting with hybrid teaching models, collaborative online learning, and innovative pedagogical approaches. By integrating virtual and physical components, SBM offers new ways to engage students and enhance their learning experiences.

Good practices include the establishment of development groups, such as those in Finland under EDUFI, which bring together institutions to share insights and strategies for improving SBM. Similar peer learning initiatives in Austria and other CEEPUS countries have created platforms for institutions to exchange experiences and develop common guidelines for blended mobility.

Promoting innovation in SBM requires targeted support for capacity building. This includes investing in digital infrastructure, offering training for staff and faculty, and providing clear guidelines for integrating virtual and physical components. Stakeholders also emphasised the importance of recognising and scaling successful practices, such as collaborative online learning projects and hybrid teaching models, to inspire other institutions to adopt SBM.

Table 2. Comparative table of blended mobility funding schemes characteristics

Theme	Erasmus+	Regional/National Programmes
Programme Design	- Standardised EU-wide framework ensuring consistency.	- Flexible, context-specific approaches tailored to local needs.
	- Clear requirements: minimum 5 days of physical mobility, 3 ECTS credits for BIPs.	- No fixed requirements for virtual components; often optional or piloted (e.g., Nordplus, CEEPUS).
	- Focus on aligning with European priorities such as inclusion and sustainability.	- Priorities vary by region: Nordplus integrates linguistic/cultural goals, while CEEPUS promotes regional collaboration.

	- Virtual components but lack detailed guidelines, leading to variability.	- Virtual components are institution-driven; Nordplus encourages them as best practices, while CEEPUS pilots specific formats.
Quality Assurance Approaches	- ESG-aligned with general QA guidance for mobility activities.	- QA is decentralised and locally adapted, with varied approaches across programmes.
	- No dedicated QA framework for blended mobility, leading to inconsistent virtual component quality.	Limited standardisation; metrics for virtual components are inconsistent or absent.
	- NAs monitor compliance with funding rules but face gaps in checking QA in SBM.	QA enforcement varies by country; - Some schemes pilot blended specific QA practices (e.g., Hungary in CEEPUS). - SEMP: Emerging QA framework for BIPs, with ongoing consultations for standardisation.
Inclusivity Priorities	- Broad participation across Europe with funding for special needs students.	- Focused inclusion efforts tied to regional demographics and goals.
	- Encourages inclusivity but lacks specific measures for blended mobility.	- Additional funding for vulnerable groups (e.g., disabilities, gender balance in CEEPUS).
	- Low awareness and promotion of inclusivity mechanisms limit their effectiveness.	- Awareness campaigns for inclusion resources are limited, leading to underutilisation.
Regulatory Approach	- Standardised across all participating Erasmus+ countries.	- Decentralised with country-specific adaptations in regional schemes.
	- Uniform heavy reporting structures.	- Regional programmes have lighter reporting requirements (e.g., Nordplus).

	<p>- Centralised funding model ensures the possibility of “consistent” access to resources.</p>	<p>- CEEPUS operates with a decentralised funding model, leading to resource variability.</p>
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4. Quality Themes

Student Blended Mobility (SBM) holds immense potential for transforming higher education through inclusivity, innovation, and international collaboration. However, its success depends on addressing critical quality themes that align with ESG standards, ensuring both internal and external QA systems function cohesively. By focusing on areas such as programme design, student engagement, and teaching excellence, SBM can deliver meaningful and equitable learning opportunities, setting a new benchmark for hybrid education in the European Higher Education Area.

The following standards of ESG Part 1 have been mentioned by QA agencies and other stakeholders as particularly relevant for an effective implementation of SBM:

4.1 Programme Design and Approval (ESG 1.2)

A key quality component in SBM is the integration of online and physical elements into cohesive and engaging programmes. Designing such programmes requires thoughtful attention to learning outcomes, curriculum alignment, and the administrative procedures that bridge partner institutions. SBM presents unique challenges in harmonising academic calendars, curricula, and credit recognition systems, often leading to delays or inconsistencies in programme execution.

Integrated curriculum design remains crucial, as coherence between digital and physical components enriches students' academic and intercultural experience. The adaptability of curriculum design to ESG guidelines ensures a balance of online and physical activities while adhering to ECTS and accreditation requirements. Therefore, institutions must develop structured frameworks that:

- Ensure SBM curricula articulate defined learning outcomes for both online and physical components, including international, intercultural, digital, and academic competencies, with the aim of enhancing particularly the academic value of the online component.
- Ensure the academic value, coherence, and purposeful sequence of both the online and physical components.
- Develop institutional guidelines to harmonise SBM components across partner universities, ensuring seamless curriculum integration, academic calendar alignment, and mutual recognition of credits.
- Involve all partners (i.e. IRO Coordinators/Officers, Teachers/Professors, Study Programme Coordinators, IT Officers, Instructional Designers / E-learning Consultants, Quality Assurance Officers – see mapping of institutional actors in SBM from WP2: Approaches to Blended Student Mobility report) during the planning phase, ensuring a clear division of responsibilities and implementation timeframes, and strategic budgeting.

- Ensure equitable internal resource allocation allowing for the design, approval and continuity of SBM aligning the strategic ambitions for SBM.

These measures reinforce the alignment of SBM with institutional and international quality standards, building on existing internal QA systems and enhancing student satisfaction and learning outcomes.

4.2 Student-Centred Learning, Teaching, and Assessment (ESG 1.3)

SBM offers opportunities to reimagine student-centred learning but faces substantial barriers to fostering engagement, particularly in its digital components. Students often report that online activities lack interactivity and personal connection, leading to lower satisfaction compared to physical components. Digital platforms used in SBM typically serve as tools for information dissemination rather than collaborative spaces for knowledge creation.

To enhance student engagement and feedback, institutions should:

- Incorporate innovative and joint teaching methodologies among teaching staff of the participating institutions (e.g., collaborative learning platforms, online kick-offs, pre-mobility orientation sessions, and post-mobility discussion or wrap-up sessions) to foster interactivity and group cohesion.
- Ensure a diversity of learning approaches enhancing inclusivity and engagement, i.e. pedagogical methods combining interdisciplinary challenges, cultural exchanges, and team-building activities.
- Ensure that the academic value, coherence, and purpose of the sequence of the online and physical components are clear and meaningful for students – students need to be aware of the learning journey and the purpose of each component from the start.
- Develop structured feedback mechanisms that extend to virtual experiences, ensuring continuous improvement.
- Establish common rubrics for student assessment across blended programmes that reflect digital, international, and intercultural competencies as essential outcomes.

By addressing these gaps, SBM can realise its potential for delivering transformative intercultural learning experiences, ensuring programmes adapt to the diverse needs and aspirations of learners.

4.3 Teaching Staff (ESG 1.5)

Teaching staff play a pivotal role in the success of SBM, but persistent gaps in professional development or staff turnover impede the delivery of high-quality learning experiences. Many

staff members lack the technical and pedagogical skills required for effective blended teaching, particularly in managing diverse groups in online and multicultural environments.

To address these issues:

- Provide staff training on digital teaching methods, international and intercultural engagement, and managing hybrid environments.
- Engage in informal learning communities allowing for bottom-up exchange of experiences, good practices, and innovative approaches in SBM (e.g., the Blended Mobility Practitioners community of practice, the European Digital Education Hub).
- Implement institutional policies recognising the workload and efforts associated with SBM through incentives, workload redistribution, equal resource distribution, or strategic alignment, allowing for the long-term establishment of SBM teams.
- Form diverse teams in advance to foster collaboration and engagement, share skills through diverse coaches and leverage technology for ongoing development.

By investing in professional development and fostering the long-term establishment of SBM teams, institutions can enhance the quality and scalability of blended learning initiatives.

4.4 Learning Resources and Student Support (ESG 1.6)

Quality learning in SBM depends on the availability and accessibility of robust resources for both students and staff. Unequal access to digital infrastructure and inconsistent support services are significant barriers to participation. Many students report insufficient pre-mobility orientation and unclear expectations for virtual components.

To create an equitable learning environment, institutions should:

- Invest in scalable technological infrastructure to ensure equitable access for students regardless of geographic constraints.
- Develop comprehensive support services, including considerations and facilities for learners with special needs, detailed pre-mobility guides, mentoring opportunities, and financial planning for underrepresented groups.
- Address the disparity in resource allocation for physical components, ensuring opportunities for enriching cultural and academic experiences abroad are accessible to all students.

These steps ensure inclusivity and access, addressing systemic barriers to student engagement in SBM.

4.5 Information Management (ESG 1.7)

Effective information management is central to ensuring continuous improvement in SBM. Despite the growing importance of SBM, feedback mechanisms and data collection processes remain underdeveloped in many institutions. Informal or fragmented data collection methods fail to capture the comprehensive insights needed to drive programme enhancements.

To improve communication and information management, institutions should:

- Employ systematic feedback collection for all SBM components, ensuring data is aggregated and actionable for programme enhancement.
- Develop information management systems to track participation rates, satisfaction levels, and learning outcomes per activity and longitudinally.
- Tailor communication for different stakeholder groups, providing clear evaluation criteria and a welcoming package for newcomers.

By adopting these strategies, institutions can create a feedback loop that strengthens the quality and coherence of SBM programmes over time.

4.6 Enhancement-Led External QA for SBM

By addressing these quality themes, institutions and QA agencies can position SBM as a driver of educational innovation. Unlike compliance-oriented approaches, enhancement-led QA emphasises the role of internal quality processes in shaping sustainable, student-centred mobility experiences. The interplay between internal QA mechanisms and external oversight fosters a culture of accountability and continuous improvement.

To foster a non-burdensome and enhancement-led external QA for SBM:

- Incorporate SBM into current institutional and programme-level quality assurance mechanisms to ensure alignment with existing accreditation processes and reduce duplication.
- Adopt enhancement-led approaches that encourage continuous improvement and flexibility for HEIs, without penalizing those not fully aligned (e.g. voluntary quality labels).
- Develop robust support systems (e.g. voluntary quality labels) to enhance quality assurance outcomes, ensuring consistent improvement across courses and programmes.
- Encourage continuous dialogue between quality assurance agencies and HEIs to develop internal quality assurance practices for SBM, particularly for small-scale initiatives likely to grow over time and to learn from existing external QA practices for blended and online learning.

4.7 Quality Themes as Pillars of Long-Term Success

Expanding on the quality themes identified, the long-term success of SBM lies in the following principles:

- **Holistic Programme Design:** SBM must be treated as a core element of internationalisation strategies, rather than as isolated initiatives. Aligning virtual and physical components within comprehensive programme designs strengthens institutional commitment to quality.
- **Equity in Access:** Overcoming barriers to participation—whether geographic, financial, or technological—is critical for fostering inclusivity in SBM. Resources must be allocated to address disparities and support diverse student populations.
- **Innovative Teaching Practices:** By investing in professional development, institutions can equip teaching staff to deliver engaging, student-centred learning experiences across all components of SBM. The involvement of COIL experts can be beneficial to understand the quality of the online component.
- **Comprehensive Data Practices:** Effective QA for SBM relies on robust information systems capable of collecting, analysing, and reporting insights across institutions. Data-informed decisions ensure that quality improvements are both targeted and scalable.
- **Inter-Institutional Collaboration:** Cooperation between universities, guided by shared standards and frameworks, enhances the scalability and sustainability of SBM. Peer learning and resource sharing play pivotal roles in this collaborative approach.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Synthesis of findings

The online sessions with stakeholders made it clear that SBM can undoubtedly be a worthwhile experience for students. The shorter, intensive and blended format appeals to those looking for an alternative to traditional Erasmus+ opportunities.

SBM presents a powerful opportunity to expand access to internationalisation, foster inclusivity, and promote innovation. However, the organisation of SBM faces some administrative, strategic, recognition, cooperation, communication, QA and skills gaps.

The Erasmus+ programme provides important funding opportunities for SBM but also brings along some procedural limitations, such as caps on applications and administrative burdens of registration, whilst funding gaps especially extend to the online component of SBM. Regional schemes rely on institutional initiatives to integrate SBM within mobility activities, rather than having specific requirements at programme level. The short duration limits the possibilities for measuring academic impact and the participation of students with special needs.

Although some universities, for instance in EUAs, have incorporated SBM into their internationalisation strategies, in most universities SBM remains a rather isolated initiative.

Inconsistent recognition of SBMs in curricula, again mostly applying to the online component, further complicates the effective implementation of SBM.

There is certainly scope for increased institutional cooperation with clear communication channels and shared SBM frameworks, including learning from relevant practices such as COIL.

Staff responsible for organising and guiding SBM often experience difficulties managing international and online groups and may lack the digital and intercultural skills to handle this effectively. As a result, students mostly perceive the online component as less engaging compared to the physical parts of the SBM. Student engagement is further diminished when online components only serve as preparation for the physical mobility, and there is limited online interactivity in e.g. BIPs. Full inclusion of domestic students in BIP courses can also be problematic if they are lacking the physical mobility perspective of international students.

QA for SBM is still in development and often relies on QA frameworks for physical mobility programmes, thereby missing out on the unique characteristics of SBM, especially regarding the learning outcomes and evaluation of the online component. Although some institutions have started to use standard student questionnaires for SBM, student feedback collection is still mainly

informal. The QA agencies report limited or no direct experience with SBM. They often focus on blended learning as a broader concept, recognising its relevance but not treating SBM as a distinct area in QA frameworks and assessments.

The barriers to SBM mentioned above can be tackled, according to stakeholders, if the following factors for successful implementation of SBM are considered:

- Financial support for educators managing blended mobility initiatives was highlighted as crucial for sustainable implementation. Therefore, institutions require consistent funding mechanisms that enable long-term planning and integration of SBM into curricula.
- Inclusion of SBM into internationalisation strategies is essential for long-term success.
- The online component of SBM should be an integral part of the whole blended mobility with a focus on maintaining high educational standards.
- Communication strategies must be tailored to different stakeholder groups, with particular attention paid to incoming participants.
- Robust support systems, including strengthened intra- and inter-institutional collaboration, are required to navigate the complexities of international mobility bureaucracy. Knowledge sharing and clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of the actors in SBM is critical.
- Conceptual clarity, guidelines, and QA frameworks for SBM are needed to help institutions fully embrace SBM. Learning outcomes and assessment methods require special attention.

5.2 Conclusions

Considering the HIBLend findings, the following conclusions regarding the possible quality approaches for SBM can be highlighted:

Conclusion 1: The current monitoring practices for SBM under the funding frameworks are limited primarily to standard numerical reporting required through predefined forms. NAs occasionally conduct audit visits to universities to support project implementation, but these efforts are not systematically aligned or standardised across countries. There is an opportunity, therefore, to enhance monitoring mechanisms that ensure consistency, quality, and a deeper understanding of institutional progress in SBM, incorporating in such monitoring activities specific indicators that can track and support the implementation, outcomes, and quality of SBM, while maintaining a balance between institutional autonomy and accountability.

Conclusion 2: The ESG provide a robust foundation for addressing the QA challenges of SBM. Key areas of focus include curriculum design, assessment methods, faculty training, IT support, learning resource availability, and systematic monitoring and reporting. By aligning both internal

and external QA processes with these ESG standards, institutions can effectively support and sustain high-quality SBM.

Conclusion 3: SBM can be aligned with internal QA by integrating requirements for an effective implementation of SBM into existing institutional and programme-level QA mechanisms. At the institutional level, it is important that cyclical audits provide the flexibility to include SBM. At the programme level, the focus could be on ensuring the cohesion between online and physical learning components in curriculum design.

Conclusion 4: Regarding external QA, enhancement-led approaches encourage continuous improvement without sanctioning institutions that are not yet fully aligned with standards for SBM. Such approaches could include a voluntary quality label for SBM and a workshop model to discuss the alignment of internal and external QA.

5.3 Recommendations

The results of the mini-Delphi studies have led us to formulate the main conclusions and quality themes for SBM, in the context of the ESG. Recommendations have already been suggested throughout the report and will now be structured according to the stakeholders with the main responsibilities for organising, funding and assessing SBM: the university management and administrative staff, the academics involved in SBM, the funding organisations and QA agencies. The following recommendations should be considered for enhancing the quality and effective implementation of SBM:

University management and administrative staff

- University management should emphasise the **strategic importance of SBM** in achieving institutional internationalisation and academic and inclusion goals.
- University management must establish clear **frameworks for inter-institutional SBM** cooperation, including standardised agreements on academic calendars, credit recognition, and harmonised processes for short-term and blended formats. Successful case studies, such as integrating SBMs into EUAs, should be shared among universities.
- University management should also establish clear **intra-institutional frameworks** for applications to SBM and the allocation of resources for SBM within the university.
- University management should invest in scalable technological infrastructure to **ensure equitable access** for diverse student populations regardless of geographic and other constraints.
- University management needs to prioritise **SBM capacity building** for administrative and academic staff, including dedicated training on developing digital skills, innovative online pedagogy, and intercultural group management.

- University management should develop institutional policies that embed the planning and execution of SBMs into the **institutional QA processes**.
- Administrative staff should develop clear rules and offer unified **administrative support** to support students during admission, studying and evaluation of SBM. The student support should include detailed pre-mobility guides, mentoring opportunities, and financial planning for underrepresented groups.
- Develop **information management systems** to track SBM participation rates, satisfaction levels, and learning outcomes longitudinally.
- Tailor **communication** for different stakeholder groups, providing clear evaluation criteria and a welcoming package for newcomers.

Academics involved in SBM

- Academics need to develop **clear learning outcomes** for online and physical components of SBM, including international, intercultural, digital and academic competences.
- Ensure that physical and online components of SBM are **integrated seamlessly** to maximise the student experience and the achievement of the learning outcomes. Involving COIL experts can help to enhance the quality of the online component.
- Incorporate **innovative teaching methodologies** (e.g. collaborative learning platforms, online kick-offs, and pre-mobility orientation sessions) to foster interactivity and group cohesion.
- Create **diverse teams** prior to the SBM activities to foster collaboration and engagement, sharing skills through diverse coaches and leveraging technology for ongoing development.
- Academics must develop **suitable assessment methods** and common rubrics for SBM, including shared assessment scales and clear pass/fail systems.
- Academics should apply **student feedback systems** to evaluate satisfaction with SBM, including digital experiences, and identify gaps.

Funding organisations

- Guidelines from National and European actors should focus on **reducing administrative burdens** associated with Erasmus+ funding, streamlining application processes, and ensuring equitable resource allocation across faculties and institutions.
- **Proactive strategies**, including targeted promotion and capacity-building, should make SBM more accessible and equitable for all students. Additionally, integrating inclusivity metrics into programme design and evaluation frameworks would encourage institutions to prioritise accessibility and equity in their SBM activities.

QA agencies

- **External QA frameworks** need to account for the specific demands of digital and hybrid delivery in mobility programmes. If QA agencies assess student mobility, they must adapt their standards to include blended mobility formats, ensuring that the digital components are adequately assessed.
- QA agencies should promote that institutions incorporate SBM into their **internal QA systems** and align it with institutional internationalisation policies.
- QA agencies should preferably apply an **enhancement-led QA approach** to SBM, guiding HEIs to develop their internal systems robustly and autonomously, ensuring long-term effectiveness.
- A **voluntary quality label** for SBM, accompanied by enhancement workshops or peer learning events, would constitute a promising combination of external and internal QA for SBM. The Estonian quality label for e-courses could serve as an inspiration for such enhancement initiatives.

6. Annexes

6.1 Annex 1. Planning of mini-Delphi sessions

Table 3. Planning of mini-Delphi sessions

Mini - Delphi Session	Date	Time	Location/ Platform	Participants	Objectives	Organisation / Facilitators
1a	27 September 2024	10:00 -12:00	Online, Microsoft Teams	2; Head of IRO and Coordinator of Alternative Internationalisation; Belgium/Flanders and Latvia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify organisational frameworks and support mechanisms. - Discuss resource allocation and inter-departmental coordination. - Examine quality assurance processes. 	European University Foundation (EUF) - Facilitated by Salome Dermati
1b	24 October 2024	10:00 -12:00	Online, Microsoft Teams	4; IROs and Institutional Erasmus Coordinator; Czechia, Finland, Poland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify organisational frameworks and support mechanisms. - Discuss resource allocation and inter-departmental coordination. - Examine quality assurance processes. 	European University Foundation (EUF) - Facilitated by Salome Dermati

2a	13 September 2024	12:30-16:30	Online, Microsoft Teams	6 HEI teachers, Finland	Discuss pedagogical approaches for blended mobility, including digital tools, assessment methods, and quality assurance.	Tampere University of Applied Sciences (TAMK) - Facilitated by Eeva Heikkilä and Jiri Vilppola
2b	9 October 2024	13:00-15:00	Online, Microsoft Teams	3 HEI teachers, Finland	Discuss pedagogical approaches for blended mobility, including digital tools, assessment methods, and quality assurance.	Tampere University of Applied Sciences (TAMK) - Facilitated by Eeva Heikkilä, Jiri Vilppola and Henri Annala
3	4 October 2024	15:00-17:00	Online, Microsoft Teams	15 students from the Czech Republic, Portugal, Italy and Germany	Explore student perspectives, including experiences in physical and virtual components, intercultural learning, and recommendations for blended mobility.	Masaryk University (MU) - Facilitated by Kristýna Hutová
4a	25 October 2024	10:00-12:00	Online, Microsoft Teams	4 senior staff members from the QA agencies AQU Catalunya, ARACIS (Romania),	Discuss the experiences of QA agencies with internal and external QA (including accreditation processes) of	The Accreditation Organisation of the Netherlands and Flanders (NVAO) - Facilitated by Mark Frederiks

				<p>FINEEC (Finland), QQI (Ireland)</p>	<p>SBM, the possible alignment of internal and external QA, and the agencies' perspectives on quality issues and ESG Part 1/2 standards that are relevant for SBM.</p>	<p>& Dagmar Provijn</p> <p>Angeliki Psychogyiou, ACA observer</p>
<p>4b</p>	<p>5 November 2024</p> <p>Response n writing: 1 November 2024</p>	<p>13:00-14:00</p>	<p>Online, Microsoft Teams</p>	<p>1 senior staff member from the QA agency HAKA (Estonia)</p> <p>senior staff members from QA agency A3ES (Portugal)</p>	<p>Discuss the experiences of QA agencies with internal and external QA (including accreditation processes) of SBM, the possible alignment of internal and external QA, and the agencies' perspectives on quality issues and ESG Part 1/2 standards that are relevant for SBM.</p>	<p>The Accreditation Organisation of the Netherlands and Flanders (NVAO) - Facilitated by Mark Frederiks & Dagmar Provijn</p>

5a	21 October 2024	14:30- 16:30	Online, Microsoft Teams	3 Programme officers from Austria, Iceland and Switzerland & 1 Coordinator from a regional funding scheme	Discuss regional and national funding schemes supporting SBM, highlighting challenges, opportunities, and alignment with institutional, regional, national and European priorities.	Academic Cooperation Association (ACA) - Facilitated by Angeliki Psychogyiou
5b	24 October 2024	10:00- 12:00	Online, Microsoft Teams	4 Erasmus+ officers from Austria, Finland and Croatia	Identify funding requirements, structural challenges, and quality assurance needs for SBM under the Erasmus+ framework.	Academic Cooperation Association (ACA) - Facilitated by Angeliki Psychogyiou

6.2 Annex 2. List of guiding questions for mini-Delphi sessions with stakeholder groups

Guiding questions for the session with HEI Admin Staff

Moderated by EUF

I. Institutional goals and objectives

1. How is SBM incorporated in the internationalisation goals and objectives of the institution/faculty?
 - a. How are these SBM related goals and objectives connected to other strategic considerations, e.g. inclusion, green transition, innovative learning experiences, employability, reputation, impact, sustainability, and funding?
2. How are SBM related goals and objectives turned into concrete action plans/study plans/projects/organisational frameworks?
 - b. Give examples of what consequences the SBM related goals and objectives have for learning outcomes, teaching and learning environment, staff and students.

II. Resources

3. What internal instruments and resources has the institution/ department/programme allocated to support SBM related goals and objectives?
4. What procedures are in place to obtain external funding?
5. What challenges do you face regarding resource allocation, and how could these be addressed?

III. Organisation

6. How is the administrative and academic staff composed/supported/ trained to support students engaging in SBM, both in the physical and digital context?
7. What SBM-specific facilities/services/support are provided by the administrative and academic staff (or other) for students engaging in SBM, both in the physical and digital context?
8. What processes are in place for the design and approval of SBM?
9. What barriers exist within your organisational structures that may hinder the effectiveness and quality of SBM?

10. What are some of the ways communication and collaboration across departments can be enhanced to improve overall efficiency?

IV. Quality assurance

11. What internal quality assurance procedures at the institutional/departmental/programme level are in place to check whether the SBM related goals and objectives are achieved and how these contribute to the quality of teaching and learning?

- a. Is it desirable to include SBM in external quality assurance procedures?
- b. If yes, how can this be done?
- c. If not, how can the institution demonstrate that the quality of SBM is assured?

12. How can we better integrate quality assurance practices into daily administrative operations?

13. What role should upper management play in ensuring consistent quality assurance throughout the organisation?

14. What are specific challenges for SBM, both in the physical and digital context and how did or will you deal with them?

Guiding questions for the session with Students

Moderated by MU

I. Motivation and preparation

1. Why did you decide to take part in a blended mobility activity (SBM-A) and what did you originally expect?

2. What did you find most helpful in getting ready for the programme, for example, information in advance or some resources, communication with the partner university or communication maybe with home university?

II. Content and curriculum

3. Could you describe your student blended mobility activities? How was it structured?

4. How did you perceive the balance between the online and in-person components of the activity and what were the strengths and weaknesses of the online sessions compared to the in-person sessions?

5. Did the student blend in mobilities activity have clear learning outcomes? Did these learning outcomes include intercultural and international aspects? If yes, which ones?

6. How effectively did the programme facilitate intercultural exchange and collaboration with students from other countries? How international was the composition of the student group and the teaching staff?

III. Outcomes

7. What new skills or knowledge did you acquire through the student blended mobility activity, did you wouldn't have gained otherwise and how do you think the blended format like the online and in-person contributed to your overall learning?

8. How were you assessed? Which assignments did you have to take to demonstrate that you achieved the learning outcomes?

IV. Satisfaction and areas for improvement

9. How satisfied are you with your student blended mobility activity overall and with the services and support provided to students specifically? And where you asked to give feedback on the quality of the mobility? If yes, how did you provide feedback on both the physical and the digital component?

10. How did you feel the programme could better support student engagement in the online session?

11. What would you suggest to improve the students' experience in the future?

12. Can you give, if you want, to give an example of a moment when the programme exceeded your expectations?

Guiding questions for the session with HEI Teaching staff

Moderated by TAMK

I. Pedagogy / digi:

1. What kind of pedagogical methods are or could be useful and increase / ensure the quality of learning?

2. What kind of digital learning environments, applications or activities are or could be useful and increase / ensure the quality of learning?

3. What kind of digital learning environments and e-learning methods and tools have you already used with good experience?

II. Design and quality learning:

4. How have you planned these mobility activities and what should be taken into account during the planning phase?

5. What kind of structure has been functional (e.g. rhythm of remote and face-to-face periods)?

6. How have you tried to ensure the quality of participants' learning in the past? How are the learning outcomes set in the curriculum assessed/could be assessed in the BIP course?

III. Organisation and development as a teacher/expert:

7. Does our organisation offer support/resources for the development / implementation of blended implementations? If not, what kind of support would you need?

8. How is blended mobility visible (or is it?) TAMK strategy / goals of your own unit or degree?

9. How does the planning and implementation of blended mobility affect your development as a teacher/expert, or does it? How could any new skills/practices that may have emerged be disseminated in the organisation?

Guiding questions for the session with QA agencies

Moderated by NVAO

I. SBM related quality assurance issues

1. What experience, if any, does your agency have regarding student blended mobility activity (SBM-A)?

2. In your view, what specific quality issues are related to SBM-A and should be addressed both in internal and external quality assurance of these activities?

3. Which parts of ESG Part 1 and ESG Part 2 are particularly relevant for the internal and external quality assurance of SBM-A?

II. Internal quality assurance

4. What (specific) internal quality assurance procedures and processes at the institutional/ departmental/programme level should be in place for SBM-A?

III. External quality assurance

5. How should external quality assurance of SBM-A be organized and what should be its focus areas? Is it desirable to include SBM-A in existing external quality assurance procedures or to develop separate procedures for the external quality assurance of SBM-A?
6. Which level should external quality assurance for SBM-A focus on: the institutional, programme or module level?
7. How much can/should the external quality assurance of SBM-A rely on or be in line with the internal quality assurance of SBM-A of the institution?
8. What kind of external quality assurance is required in view of recognition of SBM-A activities?

IV. Current state of affairs

9. Have you developed or do you know current (internal/external) quality assurance activities that allow for a specific focus on SBM-A or that can easily be adapted to deal with the specific quality issues of SBM-A?

Guiding questions for the session with Funding Agencies

Moderated by ACA

Questions for Erasmus+ Officers

I. Programme design and implementation

1. What are the funding requirements for the overall structure and design of KA1 blended mobility activities you support (BIPs and individual mobility)?
2. To what extent are these requirements part of the evaluation criteria for Erasmus+ KA1 (project) applications?
3. Are there any measures to ensure the alignment of blended activities with other priorities under Erasmus+? (inclusion, digital competence, sustainability, etc.)

II. Impact and Outcomes

4. What specific outcomes (e.g., student learning, intercultural competence, academic achievements, flexible learning paths) do you expect to see/or do you already see from the KA1 blended mobility activities (BIPs and individual mobility) you support?
5. Are there any measures to ensure that KA1 blended activities you support are accessible and inclusive to a diverse group of institutions and students?
6. How do you evaluate the performance of KA1 blended mobilities you fund?
7. Do you have any discussions on the quality related aspects of Erasmus+ KA1 blended mobilities with beneficiaries (e.g., dedicated workshops, TCAs) or other stakeholders (e.g., national QA agencies, ministries)? If yes, what kind of proxies do you use for assessing this quality, if any?
8. What are the possible obstacles in maintaining uniform quality standards for SBMAs across participating counties?

III. Challenges and opportunities

9. What challenges or limitations do you see in funding blended activities under Erasmus+, and how do you think they can be mitigated?
10. Are there any measures to encourage innovation in the design and delivery of blended activities under Erasmus+?
11. What good practices have you observed in the blended activities you have funded, and how do you promote their uptake in other initiatives?
12. How do you see the future of blended mobility in higher education, and what role do you expect your organisation to play in it?

Questions for coordinators of national / regional mobility schemes

I. Funding portfolio

1. What kind of student blended mobility activities (SBM-A) are funded or facilitated by your institution?

II. Programme design and implementation

2. What are the funding requirements for the overall structure and design of these activities?

3. To what extent are these requirements part of the evaluation criteria for SBMA (project) applications?
4. How do you ensure alignment with other national priorities for mobility? (e.g., green travel, inclusion)
5. How are funding criteria adapted to fit the unique characteristics of the involved countries in your regional programme? (Additional question for regional funding programmes)

III. Impact and Outcomes

6. What specific outcomes (e.g., student learning, intercultural competence, academic achievements) do you expect to see from the SBMAs you support (both components)?
7. How do you ensure that the SBMAs you support are accessible and inclusive to a diverse group of students?
8. How do you evaluate the performance of SBMAs you fund?
9. What quality assurance frameworks or standards do you expect to be applied for blended mobility activities that your organisation has funded?
10. What would you consider a key success factor in a SBM-A that your organisation has funded?

IV. Challenges and opportunities

11. What challenges do you see in funding SBM, and how do you think they can be mitigated?
12. How do you encourage innovation in the design and delivery of SBM?
13. What good practices have you observed in the activities you have funded, and how do you promote their adoption in other initiatives?
14. How do you see the future of blended mobility in higher education, and what role do you expect your organisation to play in it?

6.3 Annex 3. The HIBLend project

The HIBLend project was designed with an overall aim to raise interest in and enhance HEIs' capacity to develop high-quality blended mobility opportunities for students. This is done through the design, testing, and dissemination of a comprehensive framework offering guidance on quality considerations for existing models and approaches to blended mobility, and main processes related to the improvement of existing activities, as well as the set-up and delivery of new ones. The project has three major focus areas:

- 1.** The design of a comprehensive framework for quality-driven blended mobility based on:
 - a.** Different types of emerging blended mobility models and approaches
 - b.** Multi-actor quality considerations for various types of blended mobility models
 - c.** Institutional approaches to guaranteeing the quality of various types of blended mobility models at different stages
- 2.** Internal and external validation of the framework through two different test case scenarios
- 3.** Framework dissemination and uptake through an interactive digital toolbox and the community of practitioners developed throughout the project

Under the first pillar, the partners will map and structure the existing and emerging theoretical and practical models of SBM. They will also investigate quality expectations of various actors (students, academic and administrative staff, funders, policymakers) and institutional approaches to guaranteeing and controlling quality.

Methodologically, this will be done by means of mixed method involving a large-scale survey of higher education practitioners, focus groups and a mini-Delphi study based on a series of expert/stakeholder workshops with various higher education actors. These methods will be instrumental in harvesting rich qualitative data from experts and HEIs who are more advanced with the topic and evaluating its value and potential for transfer to other institutional settings.

This work will result in an informative, guiding typology of various approaches to blended mobility and an in-depth overview of the related quality expectations and institutional approaches to address them in practice. These two steps will lead to the design of a comprehensive framework offering guidance for institutions on the key principles and processes underpinning the quality of existing blended mobility programmes or the design and delivery of brand-new activities for students.

The second pillar will involve the internal testing of the framework by TAMK and MU based on their ongoing cooperation in physical and online mobility, and the external validation by interested HEIs identified through an open call for participation.

The third pillar will focus on the interactive visualisation and dissemination of the framework through a project digital toolbox, consisting of a 'heatmap' of good practice examples and institutional (e.g., video) testimonials raising awareness of quality blended mobilities among institutions and students.